

Identifying the Impacts of Digital Technologies on Labor Market: A Case Study in the Food Service Industry

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Part 01

INTRODUCTION

Introduction

Introduction

Touchscreen point of sale terminals

Order and pay at the table

Handheld point of sale systems

Contactless payments

Self-order Kiosks

Kitchen Display screens

Introduction

Labor saving

Cashier-less checkout system

Throughput increase

Transaction

Cost reduction

Increase efficiency
Reduce wastage

Customer satisfaction

Preparedness to combat
the spread of virus

Introduction

~50%

of current work activities are current occupations have more than **30%** of activities technically automated.

15%

of work could be displaced by automation by 2030.

A top-down view of a wooden table. In the center-right is a dark brown ceramic bowl filled with wide, flat pasta, topped with sautéed shrimp, sliced cherry tomatoes, and fresh green herbs. To the left of the bowl is a small, round, dark-colored pepper mill filled with a mix of black, white, and red peppercorns. Above the pepper mill are fresh green herbs and a whole red tomato. A white text box with a black border is overlaid on the image, containing the text 'Part 02' and 'BACKGROUND'.

Part 02

BACKGROUND

Knowledge Gap

Previous study

- Quantified the impact of artificial intelligence on the whole labor market
- Studied the relationship between the usage of robot, wages, and employment

Knowledge gap

- Ignored the differences between each industry
- Over-generalized the model

Why food service industry?

Labor intensive

10% total work population

The industry workforce will likely exceed 17 million by 2030

Large market scale

Huge contribution to GDP

Part 03

METHODOLOGY

Methodology

1

Data collection

Collected McDonald's financial reports from 2006-2019

2

Data extraction

Extracted data from the annual reports

Item	2019		2018		2017
	Amount	Change	Amount	Change	Amount
Revenue	\$ 8,271	4%	\$ 8,076	4%	\$ 7,774
Cost of Company-owned restaurants	11,086	1	7,075	1	7,102
Cost of Franchised restaurants	1,121	1	1,022	2	1,000
Operating income	1,064	20	979	20	672
Income tax expense	2,281	16	1,389	16	1,419
Income before income taxes	1,212	16	1,378	16	1,789
Income tax expense	2,281	16	1,389	16	1,419
Net income	\$ 1,212	16	\$ 1,378	16	\$ 1,789

3

Data analysis

Analyze and characterize the trend of the extracted data

Part 04

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Results & Discussion

Fig. 1 Total Revenue and Total Cost (2006-2019)

Fig. 2 Profit (2006-2019)

Results & Discussion

Fig. 3 Efficiency Ratio (2006-2019)

Fig. 4 Operating Income Per Employee (2007-2019)

Fig. 5 Employee per restaurant (2007-2019)

Fig. 6 Employee benefit per employee (2007-2019)

Results & Discussion

Fig. 1 Total Revenue and Total Cost (2005-2019)

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- ▶ 1. A sharp change from 2015 to 2017
- ▶ 2. McDonald's started to install self-order kiosks in 2015, and completed comprehensive installation in 2016
- ▶ **The adoption of technology, especially in the process of production and service, could enhance operating efficiency, increase profit, improve employees' benefit, and reduce the demand for employees.**

The background of the slide is a composite image. On the right, a large, light-brown potato is shown. In the lower-left foreground, a stack of several silver coins is balanced on a small metal spoon. Below the spoon, a black Kenko calculator is visible, with its display showing the number 7119115. The entire scene is set against a background of a document with a grid pattern, possibly a ledger or account book. The text 'Part 05' is centered in a dark blue rounded rectangle at the top.

Part 05

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Limitations

01 Small sample size

02 Global homogeneity assumption

03 Influence of other relevant variables

Future Work

● Examine whether the trend from McDonald's corporation is consistent with **other corporations**.

● Study the trend of different **regions**.

● Identify the similarities and differences, and find the reasons beneath those phenomena.

● **Statistically test the significance** of the impacts of technologies, and propose possible strategies to prepare for and adapt to the potential work displacements.

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Reference

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THANK YOU

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